

Analytical application of newly synthesized composite ion exchanger : Tin(IV) molybdo-sulphosalicylotungstate

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Abstract : A novel composite cation-exchanger has been synthesized via sol-gel method. It was characterized on the basis of FTIR, XRD, TGA and SEM. The structural studies reveal semi-crystalline nature of the material. The effect of temperature on the ion exchange capacity was studied. The hybrid material exhibits improved thermal stability, higher ion-exchange capacity and better selectivity for toxic heavy metal ions. The ion-exchange material shows an ion-exchange capacity of 1.72 meq g⁻¹ for Na⁺ ions. Sorption behavior of metal ions on the material was studied in different solvents. The distribution coefficient of different metal ions on exchanger is in the following order : Pb^{II} > Cd^{II} > Cu^{II} > Zn^{II} > Mn^{II} > Ni^{II} > Ca^{II} > Mg^{II} > Co^{II} > Hg^{II}. The cation exchanger was found to be selective for Pb^{II} and Cd^{II} ions. Analytically important separations of heavy metal ions from synthetic mixtures as well as industrial effluents were achieved with the exchanger.

Keywords : Ion exchanger, composite material, distribution coefficient, binary separation, waste water treatment.

Introduction

Organic-inorganic composite materials have attained a great deal of attention because of their useful integration of properties encompassing both organic and inorganic characteristics within a single molecular-scale¹. A composite material consists of two or more physically distinct components and exhibits properties that are entirely different from their original components. They have been used as sorbents², ion exchanger³, catalyst⁴ and ion selective electrode⁵. Composite exchangers are being preferred over organic and inorganic ion-exchangers as they overcome two major drawbacks from which the latter suffers. One serious limitation of organic resin is its poor thermal and chemical stability (less stable in highly acidic and basic medium) while the use of inorganic ion-exchanger is limited by its non-reproducibility⁶. Composite ion-exchangers have been found useful with definite advantages for the removal of toxic heavy metals from water bodies⁷⁻⁹. Concentrations of lead, cadmium, iron, manganese, zinc, chromium and nickel were much higher than the World Health safe limits for drinking water in all the sampled streams after they had passed through industrial areas (electroplating, lead storage bat-

tery, paper industry)¹⁰. These industrial effluents discharged into the water bodies namely river and sea; which are hazardous to human health as they cause serious damages to brain, kidney and reproductive systems, when ingested or inhaled through water or food. Both Pb^{II} and Cd^{II} disrupt the enzyme systems mediated by other metals which are important to the body – iron, calcium and zinc. The present paper reports the synthesis, characterization and industrial analytical applications of new organic-inorganic hybrid tin(IV) molybdo-sulphosalicylotungstate cation exchanger in the separation of Pb^{II} from paper industry waste water and Cd^{II} from cadmium battery industry waste water.

Experimental

Reagents : Stannic chloride (E. Merck), sodium molybdate (E. Merck), 5-sulphosalicylic acid (Loba Chem) and sodium tungstate (E. Merck) were used for the synthesis of the exchangers. All other reagents and chemicals used were of analytical grade.

Apparatus and instruments : A glass column was used for column operations. FT-IR spectrometer model Thermo-Nicolet Avtar 370 for IR studies, X-ray Diffractometer

Bruker AXS D8 Advance for X-ray diffraction studies, JEOL Model JSM-6390LV for scanning electron microscopic analysis, TG Perkin-Elmer Diamond TG/DTA Analysis System for thermogravimetric/derivative thermogravimetric analysis were used.

Synthesis of the exchanger : The precipitate of tin(IV) molybdosulphosalicylotungstate (SnMoSW) was prepared by adding gradually the solution of 0.1 M stannic chloride into the mixture of 0.05 M 5-sulphosalicylic acid, 0.05 M sodium molybdate and 0.05 M sodium tungstate with constant stirring at room temperature for 1 h whereby a gel type slurry was obtained. The resulting precipitate was kept overnight in the mother liquor for digestion. After decanting off the supernatant liquid, the remaining precipitate was washed and filtered with demineralized water to remove any excess reagent. The material was dried in an oven at 50 ± 2 °C. In order to convert the material in H^+ form, it was subsequently treated with 1.0 M HNO_3 solution for 24 h with occasional shaking intermittently replacing the supernatant liquid with fresh acid. The excess of acid was removed by washings with demineralized water and finally dried in an oven at 50 ± 2 °C. The material was sieved and kept in a desiccator.

Ion exchange capacity (IEC) : The ion exchange capacity of the material was determined by column method¹¹.

Effect of temperature on IEC : The effect of temperature on ion exchange capacity was studied¹¹.

Distribution coefficient (K_d) : Distribution studies were carried out for various metal ions in demineralized water by batch process¹².

Binary separation of metal ions : Quantitative separations of some important metal ions were achieved on tin(IV) molybdosulphosalicylotungstate columns. 1.0 g of exchanger in H^+ form was packed in a glass column (0.5 cm, internal diameter) with a glass wool support at the bottom. The column was washed thoroughly with demineralized water and the mixture of two metal ions (each with initial concentration of 0.1 mol L^{-1}) was loaded onto it and allowed to pass through the column at a flow rate 5–20 drops min^{-1} until the level was just above the surface of the material. The process was repeated twice or thrice in order to ensure the complete sorption of metal ions on the bead. The separation of metal ion was achieved by collecting the effluent in 10 ml fraction and titrated

against the standard solution of di-sodium salt of EDTA (0.01 mol L^{-1}).

Separation of Pb^{II} and Cd^{II} from industrial effluents using tin(IV) molybdosulphosalicylotungstate columns : Industrial wastewater was collected from paper and battery industries. Samples were first filtered to remove any solid particles and then it was neutralised. The colour producing substances were removed by adsorption using charcoal. The treated samples were chemically treated for the detection and separation of any heavy elements presents. 100 ml of the sample was passed and repeated 3–4 times using effluent collected at the bottom. This was for the maximum uptake of cation. Care was taken to restrict the flow by 0.5 ml/min. The eluent used for Pb^{II} and Cd^{II} were 0.5 M HNO_3 . Finally the ions were eluted out using respective eluents and then determined titrimetrically with EDTA solution.

Results and discussion

The exchanger, SnMoSW obtained as dirty white transparent semicrystalline solid having maximum ion exchange capacity of 1.72 meq g^{-1} at room temperature was selected for detailed study.

The FTIR spectra showed (Fig. 1) a broad band in the region 3500–3200 cm^{-1} confirming the presence of -OH group in the exchanger. The band with a maximum at 1622 cm^{-1} may be due to the C–O stretching of sulphosalicylate molecule¹³. The band at ~ 1384 cm^{-1} indicates the presence of structural hydroxyl protons. The band at 844 cm^{-1} indicates the presence of molybdate

Fig. 1. FTIR of SnMoSW.

group. The band maximum at 945 cm^{-1} is attributed to Sn-O-H bending mode.

X-Ray diffractogram (Fig. 2) shows some prominent peaks together with a number of low intensity peaks at different 2θ values. The analysis of these small signal peaks suggests semi-crystalline nature of the composite material. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) study was performed to examine the surface morphology of composite material. SEM photograph of SnMoSW depicted its irregular shape (Fig. 3) and the rough surface with pleats. The SEM data indicates its semi crystalline nature of the material which support with the data obtained from the XRD analysis.

Fig. 2. XRD of SnMoSW.

Fig. 3. SEM image of SnMoSW.

It was observed that on heating at different temperatures for 1 h, the ion-exchange capacity of the dried sample material was changed as the temperature increased as

shown in Fig. 4. The composite cation-exchange material was found to possess higher thermal stability as the sample maintained about 58% of the initial mass by heating up to $400\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. However, in respect to ion exchange capacity, this material was found to possess higher thermal stability as the sample maintained 90% of the ion-exchange capacity up to $150\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and it retained about 70% of the initial ion-exchange capacity by heating up to $300\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Fig. 4. Temperature effect on ion exchange capacity.

The thermogram of SnMoSW composite cation exchanger (Fig. 5) showed that the weight loss (about 10%) of the ion exchanger up to $147\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ is due to the removal of free external water molecules¹⁴. Further, a gradual loss of mass (about 5%) up to $273\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ may be due to the condensation of hydroxyl groups. Above $273\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, the gradual loss in weight (about 2%) up to $425\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ is due to

Fig. 5. TGA of SnMoSW.

the removal of structural water. Further loss of mass (about 2%) between 425 °C and 881 °C may be due to slight decomposition of the organic part of the material. When the temperature is raised a slight sharp weight loss is observed, which indicates the complete conversion of the metals into metal oxide beyond 881 °C. The percent weight loss with increasing temperature observed by TGA curve for SnMoSW is also supported by the thermal stability experiment (Fig. 4).

In order to explore the potentiality of the new hybrid

cation-exchange material in the separation of metal ions, distribution studies for metals ions were performed in different solvent systems (Table 1). The distribution coefficient data show that the material was found to be selective for Pb^{II} and Cd^{II} ions.

The separation capability of the material has been demonstrated by achieving binary separations of some important metal ions viz. Co^{II}-Pb^{II}, Ni^{II}-Pb^{II}, Mg^{II}-Pb^{II}, Hg^{II}-Pb^{II}, Co^{II}-Cd^{II}, Ni^{II}-Cd^{II}, Mg^{II}-Cd^{II} and Hg^{II}-Cd^{II} (Table 2). The separation was based on sequential elution of

Table 1. K_d values of various metal ions in different electrolyte

Metal ion	DMW	HNO ₃ (M)			NH ₄ NO ₃ (M)		
		0.001	0.01	0.1	0.001	0.01	0.1
Pb ^{II}	960.00	955.10	832.90	600.00	945.60	873.20	542.10
Zn ^{II}	52.30	46.00	42.10	31.00	42.90	38.10	22.00
Mn ^{II}	30.50	30.00	12.00	2.00	29.00	10.00	2.00
Ni ^{II}	29.00	25.00	8.00	NA	23.00	4.00	NA
Hg ^{II}	9.10	NA	NA	NA	6.29	NA	NA
Ca ^{II}	26.10	24.00	19.00	9.00	34.00	25.00	12.00
Cd ^{II}	749.60	621.00	523.80	431.20	700.00	438.90	233.60
Co ^{II}	19.86	9.00	NA	NA	16.00	2.00	NA
Cu ^{II}	308.00	73.00	46.00	29.00	80.00	73.00	66.00
Bi ^{III}	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Mg ^{II}	20.47	18.20	10.00	NA	17.00	5.80	NA

NA : No noticeable adsorption.

Table 2. Binary separation of metal ions on tin(IV) molybdo-sulphosalicylotungstate

Separation achieved	Eluent	Metal ion (mg)		% Efficiency
		Loaded	Eluted	
Co ^{II}	0.01 M HNO ₃	2.00	1.96	98.00
Pb ^{II}	0.5 M HNO ₃ + 0.5 M NH ₄ NO ₃	3.00	2.93	97.67
Ni ^{II}	0.1 M HNO ₃	2.00	1.97	98.50
Pb ^{II}	0.5 M HNO ₃ + 0.5 M NH ₄ NO ₃	2.75	2.73	99.27
Mg ^{II}	0.1 M HNO ₃	1.20	1.20	100.00
Pb ^{II}	0.5 M HNO ₃ + 0.5 M NH ₄ NO ₃	2.60	2.56	98.46
Hg ^{II}	0.001 M HNO ₃	3.00	2.88	96.00
Pb ^{II}	0.5 M HNO ₃ + 0.5 M NH ₄ NO ₃	3.30	3.18	96.36
Co ^{II}	0.01 M HNO ₃	2.00	1.98	99.00
Cd ^{II}	0.5 M HNO ₃ + 0.5 M NH ₄ NO ₃	2.25	2.20	97.78
Ni ^{II}	0.1 M HNO ₃	1.98	1.93	97.47
Cd ^{II}	0.5 M HNO ₃ + 0.5 M NH ₄ NO ₃	2.00	1.98	99.50
Mg ^{II}	0.1 M HNO ₃	6.00	6.00	100.00
Cd ^{II}	0.5 M HNO ₃ + 0.5 M NH ₄ NO ₃	9.00	8.30	92.22
Hg ^{II}	0.001 M HNO ₃	2.25	2.20	97.78
Cd ^{II}	0.5 M HNO ₃ + 0.5 M NH ₄ NO ₃	3.00	2.96	98.67

ions through the column depending upon the metal-eluting ligand (eluent) stability. The weakly retained metal ions get eluted first, followed by the stronger one. The separations are quite sharp and recovery was quantitative and reproducible.

The practical utility of the composite material was demonstrated by separating lead and cadmium from synthetic mixtures (Tables 3 and 4) as well as from industrial wastes water such as paper industry and battery industry respectively (Table 5). The specificity of this material towards lead and cadmium is the promising feature of

Table 3. Selective separation of Pb^{II} from synthetic mixtures containing Pb^{II}, Zn^{II} (2.15 mg), Mg^{II} (2.97 mg), Co^{II} (3.70 mg) and Ni^{II} (1.93 mg)

Amount of metal ion loaded (mg)	Amount of metal ion found (mg)	Recovery (%)	Eluent used (M HNO ₃)	Volume of eluent (mL)
3.10	3.05	98.39	0.5	70
2.31	2.29	99.13	0.5	50

Table 4. Selective separation of Cd^{II} from synthetic mixtures containing Cd^{II}, Zn^{II} (2.15 mg), Mg^{II} (2.97 mg), Co^{II} (3.70 mg) and Ni^{II} (1.93 mg)

Amount of metal ion loaded (mg)	Amount of metal ion found (mg)	Recovery (%)	Eluent used (M HNO ₃)	Volume of eluent (mL)
2.68	2.54	94.78	0.5	70
2.29	2.16	94.32	0.5	50

Table 5. Quantitative removal of Pb^{II} from paper industry effluent and Cd^{II} from battery industry using column of SnMoSW

Sample	Metal ion	Eluent used (M HNO ₃)	In mg/100 mL
Sample A	Pb ^{II}	0.5	1.15
Sample B	Pb ^{II}	0.5	1.23
Sample C	Cd ^{II}	0.5	0.99
Sample D	Cd ^{II}	0.5	1.73

this material, as cadmium and lead are the most potent pollutants in the environment that leads to many disorders in the body. Around 1.0 mg/100 mL lead and cadmium metal ions were separated from the paper and battery industrial effluents using SnMoSW ion exchanger column.

Conclusion

Semi-crystalline tin(IV) molybdo-sulphosalicylotungstate organic-inorganic hybrid cation exchanger shows selective sorption towards heavy metal ions. It is thermally stable and retains 70% initial ion-exchange capacity (1.2 meq g⁻¹) even after heating upto 300 °C and can be safely used at elevated temperature. It can also be used in column packing for quantitative separations of metal ions. Determination of Pb^{II} and Cd^{II} metal ions from synthetic water and industrial wastewater was effectively done by SnMoSW. The material can further be explored for the removal and recovery of metal ions from industrial effluents. The composite tin(IV) molybdo-sulphosalicylotungstate cation exchanger, thus, exhibits scavenging nature for lead and cadmium and also be used in the environmental studies.

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